

PECULIARITIES OF DIRECT AND INDIRECT SPEECH (DISCOURS DIRECT ET INDIRECT) IN FRENCH LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The use of someone else's opinion in the form of an independent sentence together with the author's speech while preserving the lexical, grammatical and semantic features of the opinion of other people is called an indirect sentence. On the other hand, a direct speech is when the author restates someone else's words while retaining the content, but adopting their lexical, grammatical, and semantic characteristics. This article discusses the specific features of direct and indirect speech in French.

Keywords: reported speech, direct speech, indirect speech, author's words, syntactic units, personal pronouns, possessives, verb tense adaptation, personal pronoun changes, use of conjunctions.

Introduction. Reported speech is the statement of another person included in the author's speech. Reported speech devices are considered as independent structures in terms of function, tone and structure of speech. Reported speech is used in both oral and written speech. In written speech, they mostly appear as dialogues. In such sentences, someone else's speech can be used, and these sentences can be directly incorporated into the speech without any changes, or they can be used in a slightly modified form. Even when reported speech is incorporated into the speech with modifications, the meaning remains unchanged. In French, there are two different ways to express the words of another person: direct speech (or direct style) and indirect speech (indirect style). In direct speech, we repeat someone's exact words. In indirect speech, we summarize or refer to what someone has said without using their exact words.

Main part. In French, direct speech (le style direct) and indirect speech (le style indirect) are important grammatical concepts used to convey someone else's words or thoughts. In indirect speech, the sentence structure changes, verb tenses are adjusted, and personal pronouns are transformed according to the new context.

Direct Speech (Discours direct) Direct speech is very simple. We will use it to impart the exact words of the original speaker and report in quotes.

Jacque dit : « J’aime les fraises ». (Jack says, “I like strawberries.”)

Lili répond : « Jean les déteste ». (Lili replies, “Jean hates them.”)

« Jean est stupide » déclare Paul. (“Jean is stupid” Paul declares)

Notice the use of « » around the quoted sentences. The quotation marks used in English (“ ”) don’t exist in French, instead the guillemets (« ») are used.

Indirect Speech (Discours indirect). In indirect speech, the original speaker’s words are reported without quotes in a subordinate clause (introduced by que).

Jacque dit qu’il aime les fraises. (Jack says that he loves strawberries.)

Lili répond que Jean les déteste. (Lili replies that Jean hates them.)

Paul déclare que Jean est stupide. (Paul declares that Jean is stupid.)

The rules associated with indirect speech are not as simple as they are with direct speech and this subject requires further examination.

Reporting Verbs for Indirect Speech. There are many verbs, called reporting verbs, that can be used to introduce indirect speech:

affirmer - to assert

ajouter - to add

annoncer - to announce

crier - to shout

déclarer - to declare

dire - to say

expliquer - to explain

insister - to insist

prétendre - to claim

proclamer - to proclaim

répondre - to answer

soutenir - to maintain

Switch From Direct to Indirect Speech. Indirect speech tends to be more complicated than direct speech because it requires certain changes (in both English and French). There are three primary changes that may need to be made.

1) Personal pronouns and possessives may need to be changed:

S	Lola déclare: « Je veux voir ma mère ».	Lola declares, “I want to see my mother.”
	Lola déclare qu’il veut	Lola declares that he wants to

S	voir sa mère.	see his mother.
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2) Verb conjugations need to change to agree with the new subject:

DS	Lola déclare: «Je veux voir ma mère ».	Lola declares, “I want to see my mother.”
IS	Lola déclare qu’il veut voir sa mère.	Lola declares that he wants to see his mother.

3) In the above examples, there is no change in the tense because the statements are in the present. However, if the main clause is in the past tense, the verb tense of the subordinate clause may also need to change:

S	Lola a déclaré : « Je veux voir ma mère ».	Lola declared, “I want to see my mother.”
S	Lola a déclaré qu’il voulait voir sa mère.	Lola declared that he wanted to see his mother.

The following chart shows the correlation between verb tenses in direct and indirect speech. Use it to determine how to rewrite direct speech as indirect speech or vice versa. Note: Présent/Imparfait to Imparfait is by far the most common - you don't need to worry too much about the rest.

	Main verb	Subordinate verb may change...
Au passé	Direct speech	Indirect speech
	<u>Présent</u> or <u>Imparfait</u>	Imparfait
	<u>Passé composé</u> or <u>Plus-que-parfait</u>	Plus-que-parfait
	<u>Futur</u> or <u>Conditionnel</u>	Conditionnel
	<u>Futur antérieur</u> or <u>Conditionnel passé</u>	Conditionnel passé
	<u>Subjonctif</u>	Subjonctif
Au présent	no change	

Conclusion. Reported speech devices are syntactic units that arise in the speech process as a result of the blending of another person's and the speaker's speech when expressing the thoughts and opinions of others. Reported speech

happens when the speaker uses someone else's thoughts in their own speech, that is, it is conveyed through the author's speech.

Direct and indirect speech are significant methods of conveying someone else's speech in French language. The selection of conjunctions, as well as tense and person adaptations, are important aspects of reported speech in French. Knowing these specific features in the structure of French is of great importance in the translation process and, moreover, in language learning.

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